
Information management in the facilities domain: investigating practitioner priorities

Abstract

Purpose - Effective information management can help real estate operators improve asset performance during use, reducing environmental impact. This exploratory study identifies and prioritises key *drivers*, *challenges* and *opportunities* relating to information management, from the point of view of a diverse cohort of facilities practitioners, with the aim of guiding future research direction and contributing to a comprehensive domain understanding.

Design/methodology/approach - Nine interviews are conducted across a broad sample of real estate sectors, the respondents including six facility managers and three data managers. A thematic analysis results in the identification, and ranking in terms of importance, of 44 emergent themes. These themes are then grouped into abstracted categories for analysis and synthesis.

Findings - The study indicates that systemic, rather than technical issues are the greatest barrier to effective information management for facilities practitioners, the interviews providing examples of practical measures which address these challenges, promoting lifecycle thinking. Alignment is also found between the facilities and data management cohorts regarding lifecycle thinking towards both physical assets and information.

Originality - The novelty of this study is the ranking and synthesis of practitioner priorities with regard to high-level information management issues, which is lacking in the literature, most studies to date focusing on case-specific technical integration.

Practical implications - This study provides direction for future developments in the facilities sector, suggesting the pursuit to address systemic issues as being both worthwhile and feasible.

Keywords: facilities, facility management, information management, practitioner interview, exploratory research, thematic synthesis, systemic, drivers, challenges, opportunities

1 Introduction

Facilities Managers (FM) play a key role in reducing the negative impacts of Real Estate (RE) on the environment, being responsible during their operational lifetime which is the most resource intensive stage (Wang *et al.* 2014). Teicholz (2018) discusses the productivity deficit in the FM domain, a result of manual retrieval, searching for information, and collecting existing or missing asset data. To address these issues, many studies have demonstrated Information Management (IM) strategies for the operational phase of the asset lifecycle such as through the use of commercial FM systems, as well as downstream use of data, such as Building Information Models (BIM), generated during development phases. But despite many integration demonstrations, and the emergence of related international standards governing data management for FMs (ISO 19650, ISO 41000 etc.), a suitable approach has yet to be widely agreed. Furthermore, a key study suggests that while other disciplines are advancing in digitalisation efforts, FMs may be experiencing reduced access to information (Quinn *et al.* 2020), likely due to the difficulty of keeping pace with technological change (Pärn and Edwards 2017).

Both Ashworth (2020) and Shaw *et al.* (2021) describe the emergent and under-defined nature of the FM domain. Due to its bottom-up and industry-led nature, considering the priorities of practitioners in planning development initiatives is considered essential (McArthur and Bortoluzzi 2018). So, with the main aim of defining appropriate research endeavours which consider the priorities of practitioners, and in order to develop a comprehensive understanding of IM for the FM domain, this paper systematically examines the sentiments of experienced facilities practitioners using a thematic synthesis methodology. It results in the development of two hypotheses around which the interviews are discussed and recommendations are proposed for future work.

The remainder of this paper consists of five sections; section 2 discusses the gap in FM research, section 3 describes the thematic synthesis methodology, section 4 presents the results of interview analysis and synthesis, section 5 discusses how the findings relate to the wider literature, and finally, conclusions are drawn in section 6.

2 Background

2.1 Information management in the facilities domain

FMs are responsible for facility performance which is directly linked to the quality of data available (NIBS 2011). Due to continued technical development, buildings, and the mechanical and electrical systems they contain, are generating increasing quantities of data (Jia *et al.* 2019), reflecting a wider global trend of data availability (Siegele 2020). So, given the importance of quality data for improving asset performance and reducing resource use, a concerning observation by Liu and Issa (2014) finds that 85% of FMs consider the information they receive from earlier lifecycle phases inappropriate for use during Operation and Maintenance (O&M). A number of authors suggest technical as well as systemic explanations for this. Some of the technical challenges are discussed by Pärn and Edwards (2017) who explain that available data delivery methods are providing excessive information, ill-suited to the downstream FM needs, including unnecessary geometric detail. Other studies discuss systemic challenges existing in the profession which can result in poor access to quality data, such as: delayed involvement in projects and the resulting inability to influence the design with maintenance considerations (Tucker and Anang Masuri, 2016; Ashworth, 2020), and the broad scope of FM activities and resulting responsibility ambiguity (Pärn *et al.*, 2017). So, while the wider Architectural, Engineering, Construction and Operations (AECO) industry is seeing increased digitalisation (Bolpagni *et al.*, 2021) the FM domain is facing both technical and systemic challenges, impeding access to information.

Where FM professionals have access to data, a range of commercial Information Technology (IT) systems are available to assist with their specific O&M needs, described in detail by Maslesa & Jensen (2020). We can broadly refer to them as Computer Aided Facilities Management (CAFM) systems. However, both Chen *et al.* (2018) and Gouda Mohamed *et al.* (2020) explain that the tools are typically expensive, siloed and continue to rely on basic, unintegrated functionality. To address the issue of incompatible data, a significant number of works in the research community focus on BIM-CAFM integration, the works of Pärn and Edwards (2017), Farghaly *et al.* (2018) and Gao and Pishdad-Bozorgi (2019) together providing comprehensive reference material on the contributions of the numerous examples. Though there is broad agreement on the potential opportunity of BIM-CAFM integration (Rogage and Greenwood, 2020), no one proposal has yet been widely adopted. In response, the research community also agree on the need for greater domain standardisation and work in this direction is evidenced by efforts such as the buildingSMART FM Handover (East *et al.*, 2021), mechanical/electrical

systems semantics alignment by Luo *et al.* (2021) and research towards more "*loosely coupled systems and open standards*" by Farghaly *et al.* (2018) and others in the linked open data community.

2.2 Considering practitioner priorities in FM research

Due to the organisational specificity of FM developments (Gao and Pishdad-Bozorgi, 2019) stakeholder engagement is considered "*key to realising the value of BIM in operations*" (McArthur and Bortoluzzi, 2018). There are two literary sources which provide collated FM practitioner viewpoints. Academic studies and industry reports. With the latter lacking the scientific rigour of peer review, we focus on the academic sources alone in this work.

A number of studies to-date employ qualitative methods to investigate FM practitioner sentiments. Both Becerik-Gerber *et al.* (2012) and Liu and Issa (2013) conduct semi-structured interviews regarding BIM adoption and experience with data quality amongst FM practitioners, while Dixit *et al.* (2019) use both interviews and surveys. Bosch *et al.* (2015) conduct a similar study using a thematic encoding approach but specific to Dutch asset managers while more recently, Durdyev *et al.* (2022) examine the FM context in New Zealand, ranking practitioner priorities, again, with regard to BIM adoption. Finally, Farghaly *et al.* (2018) use a related qualitative approach, conducting focus groups to collect information requirements for asset management functions to support BIM data exchange, while recent work by Ashworth (2020), again, employs thematic encoding of practitioner interviews to establish critical success factors for specifying FM data requirements. These works provide evidence of the effectiveness of the qualitative method in collecting the views of FM practitioners, but as we can see, are focused mainly on BIM-related processes and adoption.

In an effort to better understand the challenges in BIM adoption, several authors propose abstracted classifications or groupings. Becerik-Gerber *et al.* (2012) divide the challenges in BIM adoption for FMs into: "*process-related, organisational and technological*". Similarly, Rogage and Greenwood (2020) suggest a division of challenges in effective information handover from implementation (design and construction) to O&M into; "*communication-related, technological and the lack of awareness of available/required information by FMs and owners*". Abstraction to such classifications is part of the process of building hypotheses and can facilitate prioritisation of research efforts. For example, the latter study asserts that two of the three groupings are "*beyond the immediate control of researchers*", suggesting that academia instead focus on the technical issues which may be more easily tested under laboratory conditions. In this way, the value of a particular research direction can be empirically supported.

These previous works establish precedence for those methods employed in this study, however, the available literature lacks investigation into the broader issues around information management in the domain, Matarneh *et al.* (2019) concluding in their seminal domain review that

"Current research tends to focus on BIM-based technologies integration to enhance FM practice, rather than resolving the issues regarding facilities information management, which is considered as the backbone for successful FM practice."

Furthermore, a prioritisation of those more organisational/cultural, or what we will refer to as *systemic* issues, is similarly missing and may be helpful to guide research direction.

3 Research methods

This is an exploratory study as described by Saunders *et al.* (2016), designed to contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the FM domain. Experiences relating to IM from the point of view of FM practitioners may provide insight as to which developments be prioritised to support the lifecycle approach of their function across an organisation. For this reason, this study analyses the experience of practitioners around the following high-level subjects as they relate to IM within their business function.

- *drivers*: those aspects which motivate a business function towards a certain strategy.
- *challenges*: those aspects which hinder a business function from achieving a certain strategy.
- *opportunities*: positive aspects which either result from, or contribute to, a certain strategy.

A thematic synthesis methodology ([Figure 1](#)), described in detail by Thomas and Harden (2008), is used to analyse and interpret a series of practitioner interviews. Emergent themes are assigned a weight of significance and used to provide a ranking of participant priorities for further synthesis and analysis. It should be noted that the topics relating to IM, as perceived by an individual, may differ from overarching organisational goals (such as the financial driver in a profit-driven organisation) which are not the focus of this study. The validity of these methods to address the aim of this study is based on precedence from other similar qualitative studies within the FM domain, as discussed in section 2.2.

Figure 1 - The five steps of this exploratory study describe a method for developing, conducting and analysing practitioner interviews, and are detailed in the following sections.

3.1 Data collection

The primary data for this study are the interview transcripts. Secondary data in the form of available related literature was also examined and is referred to throughout.

3.1.1 Participant selection

As this research relies heavily on the input of practitioners, and in line with studies of similar scale in the AECO sector, quality of respondents was prioritised over quantity (Tabatabaee *et al.*, 2021; Durdyev *et al.*, 2022). Prominent organisations across a wide segment of RE sectors were identified throughout Ireland, Holland and Sweden and interview participants were selected based on their experience and role. To ensure data saturation a range of viewpoints were sought (Fusch and Ness, 2015), and given the IM focus, the interview cohort included six FMs and three data managers (DM), and both male and female (23%) participants. Interview cohort information is provided in Appendix 1.

3.1.2 Interview design

Nine semi-structured interviews were conducted by between 1 and 2 interviewers. An interview structure (summarised in Appendix 2) and consent form were provided to participants in advance of the meeting which lasted between 1 - 1.5 hours. The interview began with a presentation of the wider research topic and aims of the study as being "*to understand the drivers, challenges and opportunities*

around information management". Meetings were audio recorded with the consent of the participant and used to transcribe the interview for later analysis. The structure of the interview was not followed rigidly, but rather acted as a guide for a discussion around the main topics and leading questions were avoided, allowing themes to emerge organically. The interviews are summarised in Appendix 3.

3.2 Development of primary and analytical themes

Thomas and Harden (2008) explain that

"Thematic synthesis has three stages: the coding of text 'line-by-line'; the development of 'descriptive themes'; and the generation of 'analytical themes'. While the development of descriptive themes remains 'close' to the primary studies, the analytical themes represent a stage of interpretation whereby the reviewers 'go beyond' the primary studies and generate new interpretive constructs, explanations or hypotheses".

The following subsections describe how these stages are used in this study in detail. At each stage, consensus was sought between two researchers.

3.2.1 Extracting descriptive themes through transcript encoding

Nvivo 1.6 software is used for transcript encoding whereby sections of text are organised into emergent descriptive themes relating to *drivers, challenges and opportunities* in IM (Figure 2). For example, the sentence "we provide a wider variety of services than most organisations" (case 3) is encoded under the subject *Challenges* as the descriptive theme *Organisation complexity*. In the process of encoding each subsequent interview, the *bank* of descriptive themes is added to, resulting in a total of 44. A complete set of verbatim encoding examples is provided in Appendix 4.

Figure 2 - Nvivo 1.6 software is used for line-by-line thematic coding, organising interview transcripts into a taxonomic hierarchy of subjects, analytical themes and descriptive themes.

3.2.2 Grouping into analytical themes

The next stage of the thematic synthesis method is to group descriptive themes into logical categories. These abstracted *analytical themes* enable synthesis of several descriptive themes together around a common topic, with precedence in the works of Becerik-Gerber *et al.* (2012) and Rogage and Greenwood (2020). An example of this step can be seen in Figure 2 where several descriptive themes are grouped together as *Technical challenges*, the overall groupings provided in Table I.

Table I - 44 emergent themes are scored for importance on a scale of -1 to +1 across the nine interviews. The themes are grouped into eight logical categories for further analysis.

3.3 Ranking practitioner priorities

This step results in a ranking of descriptive IM themes based on practitioner sentiments which may help to prioritise future developments. For example, using a related method, Durdyev *et al.* (2022) interpret

practitioner sentiments from interviews according to a scale of importance, providing a ranking of topics relating to BIM adoption by FMs.

3.3.1 *Assigning a weight of theme significance per case*

Following transcript encoding each descriptive theme is assigned a weighting based on its significance during each interview. These were either; -1 ('low significance'), 0 ('some significance') or +1 ('high significance'), with 0/null assigned to cases where the theme did not emerge. The weightings were discussed by two interviewers during meetings until consensus was reached in each case. **Table II** provides the weighting of descriptive themes.

3.3.2 *Ranking priorities per cohort*

In order to compare the priorities of the two cohort groups, the analysis is broken into;

- facilities manager interviews (cases 1-6)
- data manager interviews (cases 7-9)

The average weight for each descriptive theme is calculated according to the above cohort groupings (**Table I**) and the results are ranked in terms of priority in **Table II**, *Group code* referring to the related analytical theme.

Table II - Ranking of descriptive themes in order of significance for each cohort. The observation that the top priorities of the FM cohort reflect the broad domain scope results in a further step of thematic synthesis.

3.4 *Development of hypotheses through synthesis of FM priorities*

A characteristic of exploratory research is the ability to adapt the study direction as a result of new data revelations and new insight emerging throughout (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). So, given the broad result of FM cohort priorities (**Table I**), and due to FM being the domain of focus for this study, a further step of synthesis is carried out which results in two hypotheses. This step, according to Thomas and Harden (2008) "*is the most difficult to describe and is, potentially, the most controversial, since it is dependent on the judgement and insights of the reviewers*". In this final step, descriptive themes prioritised by the FM cohort are interpreted into research hypotheses, **Figure 3** demonstrating their interrelated nature.

Figure 3 - Conceptual overlap between the broad FM cohort priorities results in a further step of synthesis providing two hypotheses of the study.

4 Results

This section describes the results of the study, including both interpretation of the ranking of practitioner priorities as well as synthesis of the interviews around emergent hypotheses. To enrich the findings for the reader, individual case summaries and sample verbatim quotes are provided in appendix 3 and 4 respectively.

4.1 Analysis of thematic ranking

The following is an analysis of the ranking presented in [Table II](#), interpreting the comparison of FM and DM cohorts, and is mainly focused on the abstracted analytical groupings.

Where the top *driver* is resoundingly a 'single source of truth' for the DM cohort, a result of the nature of their IM role, the FM cohort shares this priority equally with a number of other diverse issues. It reflects the broad scope of the FM function, one participant explaining that *"everything crosses the FM's desk"* (case 3).

Reflecting on the *challenges* we observe a clearer distinction between the priorities of FMs and DMs. Whereas the DM priorities mainly relate to technical and standardisation challenges, FM priorities focus around systemic issues such as 'organisational mindset' and 'understanding of the FM role', which, as discussed in section 2.2, may be more difficult to address (Rogage and Greenwood, 2020). An example of the challenge around organisational culture is conveyed by one participant explaining that *"a lot of my colleagues do not know what I do on a day-to-day basis, they just think I'm the maintenance man [...] they don't know all the aspects of what the FM does"* (case 2).

Finally, the key *opportunities* as perceived by the cohort are relatively consistent, only differing in the inclusion of 'building relationships with suppliers' added to the FM priorities. This reflects the growing trend towards outsourcing (Adhikari *et al.*, 2019) and its importance in the domain. It is notable that 'effective planned preventative maintenance' is perceived by the DMs as a top priority, a fundamentally FM-centred topic and a departure from earlier results for DMs which focus heavily on their data-handling role. This perhaps reflects their appreciation of the priorities of the FM discipline they support, and confirmation that they too view information management as being instrumental in maintaining buildings over their lifetime.

In summary, though the DM cohort prioritise technical issues, reflective of their business function, while the FMs focus on a more broad set of themes and particularly *systemic* ones, the overall priorities appear to be relatively consistent. This suggests alignment in mindset and a shared awareness of the importance of effective IM for longevity of the real estate assets under their administration.

4.2 Interview synthesis

In the following sub-sections the interviews are synthesised around two emergent hypotheses as described in section 3.4 and conveyed visually in [Figure 3](#).

4.2.1 Information management is being driven by key individuals using innovative methods

In almost all cases, it appears that fundamental IM change is being driven, not top-down by an informed organisation, but by forward-thinking individuals. One participant even described an attempt at top-down IM as having been *"traumatising"* where an integrated system was imposed but which *"did not consider the day-to-day needs of users"* and *"resulted in push-back"* (case 6). They felt that *"facility managers are under pressure to accept, and in some cases manage, systems that are not suited to do the job"*. To address such misalignment, a number of participants described a user-centric approach to

IM implementation, including key contractors in designing the systems (cases 1, 2, 5 and 8), one participant explaining that *"we see our specialist contractors as an extension of our team"* (case 5), a sentiment echoed across the cohort. Despite such grassroots efforts, top-level buy-in will typically be required to invest in effective IM and various participants described ongoing negotiations with upper management around a suitable system. *"We've just been given the green light, in principle"* (case 8) suggesting evidence of successful negotiations.

Perhaps most interestingly, several participants describe their own innovative communication techniques which are garnering buy-in from the wider organisation and stakeholders. The participant in case 2 describes cross-domain data federation to convey the carbon reduction effects of FM interventions, justifying their innovative approach by explaining that *"I needed to be able to regularly report, to the wider organisation, the carbon reduction metrics, across what are now siloed systems"*. In case 1, interdepartmental IM meetings *"are building trust"* and having a gradual but positive effect on organisational culture. Finally in cases 6 and 8, total-cost-of-ownership financial forecasting for capital investment decisions is highlighting the often-ignored cost of maintenance, a result in both cases of collaboration between IT and FM departments. And so, the interviews demonstrate that key individuals appear to be driving both IM practice, and in some cases wider culture change within their organisation, towards an FM lifecycle mentality for both real estate and the information used to manage it.

4.2.2 *Lifecycle thinking, characteristic of practitioners towards real estate, extends to information management*

The maintenance of systems over their usable life falls into the typical FM scope. Given that operational expenditure (OPEX) typically far outweighs capital expenditure (CAPEX), accounting for around 75% of lifecycle cost (Grzyl *et al.* 2017), considering the lifecycle view (or *total-cost-of-ownership* as discussed above) in decision making is an important function of the FM role. Another important and related function is the outsourcing of specialist services. Economically speaking, from a suppliers' point of view, it is in their best interests to make themselves indispensable to the client (Shawosh and Nicholas, 2019), and this risk of vendor lock-in emerged as a theme during the interviews. With respect to physical systems, one well informed FM team (case 4) conveyed an acute awareness of the risks with closed protocols for mechanical systems, being careful to avoid them during procurement. The question arises as to whether this precaution can be extended into IM strategy.

Throughout the interviews, the FM characteristic of lifecycle thinking towards built assets is similarly evident with regard to IT systems. One participant, recognising the risk of vendor lock-in when procuring a commercial integrated FM system, reported *"looking at the direction the service provider is leaning to make sure it aligns with our future facilities needs"* (case 5) while another expressed a feeling of a lack of available options in the market, expressing with resignation *"it's the [major vendor] way or the highway"* (case 6). Another related sentiment was that the required knowledge to oversee such IT migration is not a typical competency of FM teams (case 2, 3, 4, 5, 8) and that, due to the underdefined role, this responsibility was, in some cases, inadvertently landing with the facilities department. Whether it is developing a unique system (case 1) or procuring a commercial integrated workplace management system (IWPMS) (cases 2, 3, 5, 6 and 8) the required due-diligence to secure a sustainable solution which will fit the organisations' future needs, is *"complex and not a core-competency"* (case 3). A number of participants report looking to larger existing customers of the prospective vendor for reassurance of suitability (cases 5, 6 and 8), and considered the service, or *integration period*, as being crucial to an effective implementation.

As was clear from the ranking of perceived opportunities (Table II), open standards emerged as being of great importance across the cohort groupings, a direction which can address concerns around proprietary systems and vendor lock-in. Discussing one such initiative (case 9), the motivation for developing their open-source asset management data model was *"the realisation that the built environment is now where earlier software was, vertically integrated platforms" and "a hostage situation"* where solutions are being *"developed against a proprietary vendor rather than a standard"*. Their approach towards *"portability of applications based on a common data model"* is referred to by another participant as *"IT independence"*, a state towards which they (case 1) are now migrating. These ideas, they explain, are *"starting to pick up speed incredibly fast"*, even being adopted by some governments in structuring their public data (Folmer *et al.*, 2020). This view is also reflected by widespread interest within the research community, specifically in the work of the *World Wide Web Consortium Linked Building Data Community Group* and others.

As is well established, FMs view built assets over their lifetime. The key takeaway is that it appears that this characteristic extends similarly towards *information*, for which more sustainable solutions are needed in the long term.

5 Discussion

As described at the outset, the majority of FM research to date has focused on BIM-CAFM integration but has largely ignored more systemic IM topics, and where authors have classified IM challenges into abstracted categories, a focus on the technical rather than systemic issues is considered as being more within the grasp of researchers (Rogage and Greenwood, 2020). This study, however, demonstrates that systemic issues, which were perceived as the greatest *challenge* by the FM cohort, are being addressed by practitioners through innovative communication. Participants describe examples and, at least anecdotally, report tangible effects on organisational culture, particularly around understanding of FM objectives. Namely the consideration of assets over their operational lifetime including not just the CAPEX but the OPEX, which is often ignored in short sighted decision making (Ashworth, 2020). Evidence of such improvements in communication demonstrate that further investigating practical solutions to systemic FM issues may be both feasible and worthwhile as it would address the priorities of practitioners and the *"backbone of successful FM practice"* (Matarneh *et al.*, 2019). It also suggests that FMs may be well placed to drive wider organisational change, perhaps a result of their people-focused and interdisciplinary nature (Cotts *et al.*, 2014).

It is evident from the closely aligned view of the key *opportunities*, there exist parallels between the FM and DM mindset with regard to their tendency towards lifecycle thinking. Furthermore, evidence that collaboration between those departments (as in cases 6 and 8) resulted in whole-life costing, suggests that closer cooperation between these functions may be a beneficial strategy to support data-driven whole-life decision making, this proposition supported by the work of Marcinkowski and Gawin (2020).

Across all subject areas, the prioritisation of issues stipulating a need for greater standardisation (driver: 'IT scalability', challenge: 'unstructured data' and opportunity: 'open standards') reflects the resounding consensus within the research community of the potential benefits. This consensus is evidenced by the works of Balaji *et al.* (2016) and Luo *et al.* (2021), as well as ongoing efforts within standardisations bodies such as ISO (*Technical committee 267*) and ASHRAE (*Semantic Interoperability-Working Group*), towards open standards for building operators. This study supports continued effort, however challenging, in this direction and we suggest that FM views be considered as a priority in

standardisation efforts, being the custodians and operators of the built environment on behalf of asset owners, and already exhibiting a well-formed concept of future information needs.

5.1 *Limitations and future work*

Sector specific traits affect the drivers of IM. Within the study sample, public bodies feel the most external pressure towards carbon reporting, local authorities tend to have a more diverse set of assets to manage than a commercial FM, while ownership models versus tenancy models also affect the scope of IM needs. A wider study could include RE segments such as: data centres, retail, manufacturing and hospitality, to provide a more comprehensive range of views. Furthermore, this study focuses on the Northern European FM sector, so further interviews are required to establish the global generalisability of the findings.

Qualitative research methods have some subjectivity by nature and so, on the recommendation of Thomas and Harden (2008), we reduce this risk by communicating the methods as clearly as possible. Though effective for the exploratory context of this study, a more detailed weighting system as, for example, in the work of Durdyev *et al.* (2022), may provide more granular and discerning results.

The prioritisation of FM challenges in this study suggests a need for future work addressing systemic rather than technical issues, an area currently underrepresented in the literature (Matarneh *et al.*, 2019). It was also demonstrated that addressing these issues may not in fact be insurmountable for researchers with demonstrations of, for example, culture change and cross-domain understanding reported in a number of interviews. And so, our future work will aim towards further interdisciplinary understanding, utilising information federation as a mode of communication of FM lifecycle thinking.

6 Conclusion

Effective IM can help real estate operators improve asset performance during operation, reducing negative environmental impacts. However, a myriad of well-documented challenges restrict the efficacy of IM practice. For example, the significant disconnect between the design/construction and operational building phases. The volume of FM research to date which addresses technical issues around IM, such as interoperability between BIM and CAFM systems, would suggest these as the key domain challenges. In contrast, this exploratory study suggests that practitioners are more concerned with underlying systemic issues than technical ones, and though most have been identified in the FM literature, tackling these systemic challenges is considered to be beyond the remit of academic research. We challenge that position by investigating the fundamental issues driving and impeding information management, as seen by facilities teams on the ground, with the aim of contributing to a more comprehensive domain understanding.

Through a series of semi-structured interviews across a broad segment of real estate sectors, sentiments are collected regarding information management in practice from a careful selection of experienced facilities practitioners. Using a thematic synthesis methodology responses are classified and ranked for significance, establishing a list of priorities. The ranking suggests that practitioners are primarily concerned with systemic issues around information management and we find evidence of practical steps being taken to resolve them, challenging the assumption that such objectives are insurmountable to address. Furthermore, a synthesis of the interviews is provided around the cohort's key information management issues. Emerging hypotheses suggest potential benefits from closer alignment between FM and IT functions, and recommends the inclusion of the FM voice in developing greatly needed interdisciplinary standards, the domain practitioners demonstrating a well-formed

understanding of future information needs. Our future work will test these hypotheses, employing cross-domain information federation as a means to advocate the FM lifecycle mindset, with the aim of addressing systemic domain issues.

Acknowledgements

Appendix 1. Interview participant information

Appendix 2. Interview structure

Appendix 3. Interview summaries

Appendix 4. Coding examples

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